

ISic0473

Dedication to the Concordia of the Agrigentines

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

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Principal Contributor

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Autopsy

2018.07.17 Prag

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

Found in the area of the Temple of Concord in the C16 AD

Coordinates

37.289670, 13.592091

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale Archeologico Pietro Griffo, inventory C1970 (?)

Physical Description

A large slab of white marble, intact on all sides (a break on the lower right corner/right side has been repaired). Two rectangular clamp holes are visible on the top, and a further two on the base. The front is finished, but not polished; the sides are rough finished; the rear is smooth.

Dimensions

Height 102.5 cm

Width 81 cm

Depth 14-15.5 cm

Layout

Seven lines of large Latin letters, centred on the stone. The planning of the text is uneven, with awkward word-breaks (lines 1-2 and 3-4, and some compression at line end, especially line 5)

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Tall, slightly curved letters, mostly with minimal serifs. P is open; R is closed with long tail; E has short horizontals of equal length, slightly upward curving; M is four equal slanting strokes. In line 5 the O and C of 'procos' are intelinked, and the following O is small and mid-line. A large diagonal upward stroke is visible above the first letter of each of the civic ethnics; and a horizontal above the Q at the end of line 6. The letters all show traces of dark paint (modern?).

Letter heights:

Line 1: 65-71 mm

Line 2: 68-74 mm

Line 3: 70-74 mm

Line 4: 72-75 mm

Line 5: 67-72 mm

Line 6: 67-74 mm

Line 7: 74-78 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: 50-52 mm
Interlineation line 2 to 3: 47-51 mm
Interlineation line 3 to 4: 50-52 mm
Interlineation line 4 to 5: 50-53 mm
Interlineation line 5 to 6: 52-55 mm
Interlineation line 6 to 7: 45-52 mm

Text

1. Concordiae · Agrigenti
2. (vac.undefined)norum(vac.undefined) sacrum(vac.undefined)
3. res publica Lilybitano
4. rum (vac.undefined) dedicantibus
5. M(arco) · Haterio Candido prôco(n)s(ule)
6. et L(ucio) · Cornelio Marcello (vac.undefined)q(uaestore)
7. (vac.undefined)pr(o) (vac.undefined) pr(aetore) (vac.undefined)

Apparatus

Text based on autopsy

Translation (en)

Sacred to the Concordia of the Agrigentines; the republic of the Lilybaetani (set this up); Marcus Haterius Candidus proconsul and Lucius Cornelius Marcellus quaestor pro praetore joined them in dedicating (it).

Translation (it)

Consacrato alla Concordia degli Agrigentini, la città di Lilibeo: dedicanti Marco Aterio Candido proconsole e Lucio Cornelio Marcello questore propretore

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491698

EDR 142394

EDCS 21900533

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CONCORDIAE AGRICENT
NORVM SACRAE
RESUBLICAE LIBERTATI
QVAM DEDICAVIT
M. PATERIO CANDIDO PROCO
S. P. L. CORNELIO MARCELLO S.
P. R. P. R.

Photo M. Metcalfe